

Design Considerations for Accelerated Life Tests Conducted on Cable Hardware Subject to Cathodic Delamination

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Abstract— The accelerated life test (ALT) is a tool used by cable manufacturers and cable end-users to determine how long a given piece of hardware will last once deployed into the marine environment. To conduct an ALT, the failure mechanism for the hardware in question must be known, and the kinetics of that process must be determined via experimentation. Typically, Arrhenius kinetics are assumed and the activation energy for the dominant degradation process must be measured. Cathodic delamination is a major failure mechanism for undersea cable connectors. Although the mechanism via which cathodic delamination weakens/destroys metal-polymer bonds is well known, good quality kinetic data for the process (from which Arrhenius activation energies can be derived) is generally lacking. Our research into the cathodic debonding process has revealed that there are three major cases that must be examined separately to obtain the kinetic parameters needed to make the time-temperature conversions for an ALT. Case (1) concerns thin polymer films (e.g., paints) applied directly over, and completely covering, a cathodically-polarized metal surface. Here, the water and oxygen needed for the cathodic reduction of dissolved oxygen reaction on the metal surface can diffuse directly and rapidly through the polymer layer. Two different methods for calculating the diffusivity of water through the polymer layer will be discussed. Once water diffusivity at three different temperatures has been measured, the natural logarithm of the diffusivity values can be plotted versus the reciprocal absolute temperature to obtain the slope of a line from which the Arrhenius activation energy for water diffusion through the polymer can be calculated. Cases (2) and (3) involve macroscopically thick layers of polymer with exposed polymer/metal bond lines. If metal-polymer bonds susceptible to attack by cathodic delamination are present, debonding will proceed inwards from the exposed edges. Measurements of the rate at which the width of the debonded region grows at three different temperatures can be used to calculate an Arrhenius activation energy. Case (3) is more difficult because it concerns materials/coatings that are resistant to cathodic delamination; no obvious debonding occurs during the early part of the ALT. For this case, a reaction acceleration factor (RAF) must be experimentally determined by measuring the corrosion current density (i_{corr}) for the reduction of water reaction using the two metals involved (usually a sacrificial anode and the metal surface of interest). The i_{corr} value for the sacrificial anode/metal substrate pair is measured using a potentiostat at the anticipated service temperature and also at the intended ALT temperature.

The ratio of these two values is the RAF and can be used directly to determine time-temperature conversion factor for the ALT.

Keywords—cathodic delamination, cathodic disbondment, cable connectors, accelerated life testing, adhesion, activation energy

I. INTRODUCTION

It has long been noted [1] that polymeric coatings and paints debond from cathodically polarized metal surfaces. The chemical reaction most often responsible for this phenomenon [2,3] (hereafter referred to as “cathodic delamination” or “cathodic debonding”) is the reduction of dissolved oxygen in water to generate hydroxyl ions:

The cathodic potential and current driving this reaction almost always originates from a cathodic protection system deliberately installed to prevent the metals in crucial pieces of hardware from corroding, but in some occasions, it can also arise from galvanically mis-matched metals being joined together in an electrolyte. The hydroxyl ions are generated at the metal-polymer interface where they create an extremely alkaline/high pH environment that weakens and degrades most metal-to-polymer bonds, eventually causing their failure.

Cathodic delamination is a major repair/refurbishment problem for the U.S. Navy, which protects the hulls and outboard machinery of naval vessels from anodic corrosion by some form of cathodic protection (either sacrificial anodes or an induced current cathodic protection – ICCP- system). Even hardware not directly connected to the cathodic protection system itself can become cathodically polarized by being connected directly to a protected hull, or to any other metal object (such as a hull penetrator) that is connected to the hull. Cathodic delamination is thought to cause hundreds of millions of dollars of damage to marine hardware every year.

Cathodic delamination proceeds via two different pathways depending upon the thickness and geometry of the polymer bonded to the cathodically polarized metal surface. The first

pathway (figure 1) occurs when the polymeric coating is “thin and infinite.” In this instance, the term “infinite” means that there are no exposed metal/polymer bond lines. An example of such an item would be a piece of metal completely coated with paint. For such items, the water and oxygen needed for the cathodic delamination reaction must diffuse through the polymeric coating/paint to reach the cathodically polarized metal surface. The second pathway (figure 2) is found on items of hardware on which there are exposed metal/polymer bond lines, and the polymeric coating is macroscopically thick. A good example of such a piece of hardware is an outboard cable connector on which there is often an exposed bond line between the metal backshell and the overmold/encapsulant. In this case, cathodic delamination proceeds via the exposed bond lines and moves inwards as a coherent front. Figure 3 is a photograph of an outboard cable connector on which cathodic debonding has occurred from the exposed backshell/encapsulant bond line inwards.

Fig. 1. Example of a “thin, infinite” coating (yellow) surrounding a cathodically polarized metal object (gray). Cathodic delamination must attack such bonds through the coating (indicated by the arrow).

Fig. 2. Example of a “thick, finite” coating (yellow) bonded to a cathodically polarized metal object (gray). Cathodic delamination attacks such bonds via the exposed bond lines (indicated by the arrows).

Fig. 3. Photograph of an outboard cable connector suffering from cathodic delamination. The debonding has proceeded inward from the backshell/encapsulant bond line as indicated by the yellow arrow. Approximately three quarters of the encapsulant has debonded from the backshell. (dark area versus lighter area)

To determine if a given coating or paint exhibits long-term

resistance to cathodic debonding an accelerated life test (ALT) is usually run. Most ALTs are based upon Arrhenius kinetics and allow years or decades of real-life exposure to be simulated by weeks or months of exposure at elevated temperatures in the laboratory. The theory behind accelerated life testing has been covered elsewhere [4] and will not be repeated here. The most important equation for the design of an ALT is the “reaction acceleration factor” or “RAF” equation:

$$\frac{TF_1}{TF_2} = RAF = e^{\frac{-E(T_2-T_1)}{R(T_1T_2)}} \quad (2)$$

The RAF equation is based upon the ratio of the time an item takes to fail at its normal operating temperature (T_1) divided by the time it takes to fail at the higher temperature the item is exposed to during the ALT (T_2). The major problem with constructing an ALT is that “E”, the Arrhenius activation energy value in the exponent of the RAF equation, is often unknown and difficult to determine experimentally. The bulk of this paper is dedicated to describing some experimental approaches for the measurement of “E” or in some cases, the “RAF” itself, for hardware exposed to cathodic delamination conditions. Further use and refinement of these ALT activation energy/RAF measurement techniques and methods will help ensure that premature, cathodic delamination-induced hardware failures in the Fleet are minimized, thereby lowering the total ownership/lifecycle cost of cables and other kinds of outboard hardware.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A. Materials

Although other cable connector backshell alloys are in use, our experiments exclusively used monel 400 alloy as the metal substrate. Monel 400 is a nickel-copper alloy that exhibits moderate corrosion resistance when immersed in seawater. Monel 400 flat-bar stock was machined into rectangular coupons 4 x 1 x 0.25 inches in size. A 10-32 threaded hole was made on the flat side of the coupon opposite the bonding surface for the attachment of sacrificial zinc anodes. For the potentiostat samples, small pieces of monel 400 and Navy anode grade zinc were prepared (about 3.0 square inches in area).

To simplify the experimental parameters, only one of the two Navy-approved commercially available primer and polyurethane encapsulant combinations was used to make samples for the activation energy and RAF measurement experiments. The primer, PR-420, and the polyurethane, PR-1547 amber, were manufactured by PRC-DeSoto. The PR-1547 polyurethane was purchased as pre-mixed and flash-frozen product in 6.0 fluid ounce plastic tubes. For experiments used to measure the uptake of water into the polyurethane, the samples were immersed in distilled water. For cathodic delamination experiments, the samples were immersed in a salt solution (3.5% sodium chloride by weight). The zinc

anodes attached to some samples were standard zinc boat rudder anodes (slightly “domed”, disc-like shapes approximately 1.5 inches in diameter and 0.25 inches thick at the top of the “dome”; see figure 4).

B. Sample Manufacture

The center two square inches of the monel 400 coupons were sandblasted with 80 grit aluminum oxide and then rinsed/cleaned with acetone prior to primer being applied to the bonding surfaces. The bonding surfaces were brush painted with one coat of PR-420 primer. The primer was allowed to air-dry for 2-4 hours before the samples were placed into a specially-designed metal mold (capable of making nine samples at a time) and PR-1547 (amber) polyurethane was poured into the mold. The mold was heated at 80°C for a minimum of 16 hours in an oven to cure the polyurethane. Figures 4 and 5 show what finished flat-bar monel samples looked like (with zinc anodes attached) before being placed into the ALT tank.

Fig. 4. Peel sample ready for testing. This sample has a sacrificial zinc anode attached to its backside. Note the overhang of the polyurethane substrate over the end of the metal substrate. Only the center two square inches of the metal coupon are bonded to the polyurethane.

Fig. 5. A set of twelve individual peel samples hung by their tails from stainless steel rods fitted into slots on top of the acrylic holder-racks, before immersion in a salt water test tank.

Once the polyurethane had cured, the samples were removed from the metal mold, cut apart using a band-saw, and their edges were sanded flush so that no primer or polyurethane extended over their sides. A small hole was drilled into the polyurethane “tail” of the samples to allow them to be suspended from a metal bar attached to an acrylic rack used to hold them upright in the salt water filled test tank (figure 5).

Samples that were going to be exposed to cathodic delamination conditions had small zinc sacrificial anodes attached to their backsides (via a nylon screw) before they were placed into the holder racks.

Samples of polyurethane used for the water absorption/diffusivity measurements were cut from 1/16 inch thick sheets of polyurethane that had been cured for a minimum of 16 hours at 80°C. Discs 2.5 inches in diameter were cut from these sheets and used in the water absorption experiments.

C. Experimental Procedures

Water absorption experiments were conducted by placing each polyurethane disc into its own beaker containing 300 ml of distilled water. Each disc rested on a bed of glass marbles to ensure water was in contact with all sides of the sample. The beakers were covered with a polyethylene bag that was secured with a rubber band. The samples were randomly divided into three equal batches (three samples each), and these batches were maintained at three different temperatures for the duration of the experiment. Periodically, the polyurethane discs were removed from their beakers, patted dry with a paper towel, and then weighed. Once weighed, the samples were returned to their beakers. The periodic weighing of the samples continued until each sample’s weight gain versus time plot leveled off (i.e., the sample had become saturated with water).

Diffusion constants for each sample set were calculated using two different methods [5,6]. The results from the two methods agreed well with each other. To obtain the activation energy for the diffusion of water through the two polyurethanes, the natural log form of the Arrhenius equation was used:

$$\ln D = -(E_a/RT) + \ln C \quad (3)$$

As the equation indicates, a plot of the natural log of diffusion constants versus 1/T (temperature in Kelvin) should be linear with a slope of $-E_a/R$ (the activation energy divided by the gas constant) if the process being studied follows Arrhenius kinetics.

Conditioning of the peel test samples was conducted at three different temperatures (23°C, 40°C, and 55°C). For each temperature, 24 samples (with sacrificial zinc anodes attached) were placed in a holder rack and submerged in the 3.5% NaCl solution. Every other day, pure oxygen gas was bubbled into the salt solution tanks for 15 minutes to maintain the dissolved oxygen content of the solutions. Each week, three samples were removed at random from the test racks and pulled to failure on an Instron machine in accordance with reference [7]. The average peel strength and failure mode for each sample were recorded.

The potentiostat experiments were run using a Gamry Reference 600 Potentiostat/Galvanostat/ZRA. A standard Gamry plastic reference cell was used with a zinc sample mounted on one side of the cell and a monel 400 sample mounted on the opposite side. A Tenney Benchmaster environmental chamber was used to keep the cell at the

selected temperature. The distance between the potentiostat and the cell inside the environmental chamber necessitated the use of a Gamry ECM8 electrochemical multiplexer unit between the potentiostat and the test cell. A standard calomel electrode (SCE) served as the reference electrode in the test cell. The solution within the test cell was 3.5% sodium chloride, and it was aerated with compressed air via a diffuser stone to ensure the equilibrium amount of dissolved oxygen was present in the salt solution during the experiments.

The samples were brought to the desired temperature (between 10°C and 66°C) within the environmental chamber and the two metals were allowed to interact with each other. After some time had passed, the Tafel lines intersected with each other, thereby indicating the corrosion voltage and current density for the zinc/monel system. The current density at the corrosion voltage was measured and the ratio of two current densities was used to calculate the RAF for each pair of temperatures.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Water Diffusion Activation Energies

Once the polyurethane discs in the water absorption experiments became saturated with water, diffusion constants for each temperature were calculated [5,6] and the Arrhenius activation energies for the diffusion of water through the polyurethane was determined. Using the method of Crank [5], the activation energy value was 3.5 kcal/mole for the PR-1547 polyurethane; using the method of Aminabhavi *et al.* [6], the activation energy value was 2.7 kcal/mole for the same material. The average value for the two methods was:

PR-1547 (amber): 3.1 ± 0.5 kcal/mole

B. Direct Cathodic Delamination Kinetics

Samples placed into the salt water solution tanks with sacrificial zinc anodes attached experienced cathodic delamination conditions. Once removed from the ALT, the samples exhibited a “window-frame” debonding pattern (figure 6). The samples debonded from their exposed edges inwards so that as time in the test tank increased, the amount of primer/polyurethane still bonded to the metal surface decreased.

Fig. 6. Example of a peel test coupon exposed to cathodic delamination conditions for 7 weeks at 23°C. This sample was made using the PRC-DeSoto system. Note the “window-frame” debonding pattern.

Eventually, the “window-frame” of debonded primer/polyurethane increased enough in width to encompass the entire test coupon (figure 7). In all cases where the “window-frame” failure mode was observed, the primer

debonded from the metal substrate, and it debonded more rapidly as the temperature of the ALT increased. This type of failure was only observed on samples subjected to cathodic delamination conditions, and it is considered to be characteristic for the cathodic disbondment of peel samples with exposed edges.

Fig. 7. Increase of the width of the debonded, “window-frame” region as a function of time for peel samples made using the PRC-DeSoto system and kept under cathodic delamination conditions at 40°C for a period of 8 weeks. Each sample represents one week of elapsed time moving from left to right.

Because the width of the “window-frame” debonded region increased as a function of time, it could be used as a variable to calculate the debonding kinetics for samples exposed to cathodic delamination conditions. A plot of the width of the “window-frame” debonded region versus the square root of time is presented as figure 8:

Fig. 8. Plots of the width of the debonded, “window-frame” region (in mm) versus the square root of elapsed time (in days^{1/2}). The pink data are for samples maintained at 55°C; the green data are for samples maintained at 40°C, and the blue data are for samples maintained at 23°C.

These plots are linear over the temperature range used in our cathodic delamination experiments – the R^2 values are greater than 0.957 for all of the lines in the plot. The slopes of the data trends for each temperature in figure 8 were squared to obtain

units of area/time. These squared slopes were then used in the natural log version of the Arrhenius equation (equation 3) to obtain the activation energy for the cathodic delamination process:

PRC-DeSoto system: 8.4 kcals/mole

C. Potentiostat Measurement of Cathodic Delamination Rate

Figure 9 is a plot of the corrosion current density versus absolute temperature for the zinc/monel 400 couple. Because the area of the electrodes is the same for each run, this corrosion current density reflects the rate of the cathodic delamination reaction (equation 1) on the monel 400 substrate when the driving voltage is supplied by coupling monel 400 to zinc:

Fig. 9. Plot of corrosion current density versus temperature for the zinc/monel 400 couple.

Fig. 10. Plot of voltage versus temperature for the zinc/monel 400 couple.

Figure 10 is a plot of voltage versus temperature for the zinc/monel 400 plot. The voltage remains rather constant with a very low over-potential for the temperature range of interest.

Figure 9 can be used to calculate a “RAF” for the cathodic delamination reaction by taking the ratio of any two of the current density values. Assuming an ALT run at 66°C with a normal service temperature of 10°C, the RAF is 3.0. That means four months in the ALT is equivalent to one year at the real service temperature. The results for the water ingress study and the window-frame debonded area growth study both yielded Arrhenius activation energies rather than RAFs, but RAFs for those cases can be calculated using equation (2), and assuming the same ALT and service temperatures as the calculation above. The results for all three methods are presented below, normalized for the ALT design:

Method	RAF	EY (months)
Water diffusion through PU	2.8	4.3
Measurement of CD reaction rate	3.0	4.0
CD Window-frame debond growth	12.1	1.0

In the above chart, the term “EY” means the length of an “equivalent year” in months for an ALT based upon the calculated RAF.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

As has been demonstrated, it is possible to calculate a “reaction acceleration factor” for an accelerated life test under cathodic delamination promoting conditions by three different methods. The first method requires the calculation of the Arrhenius activation energy for the diffusion of water through the coating over the cathodically polarized metal surface. This particular method is mostly applicable to very thin coatings with no exposed edges (like painted objects) for which water and oxygen have to diffuse through the coating to generate the hydroxyl ions on the surface of the metal. The other two methods are applicable to items of hardware for which the coating is macroscopically thick and for which there are exposed metal/coating bond lines. In such cases, cathodic delamination always proceeds from the exposed bond lines inwards, and nothing of any consequence is believed to diffuse through the coating to access the metal.

The reason there are two different methods for macroscopically thick coatings with exposed edges has to do with the resistance of the coating to cathodic delamination. If the coating is readily debonded, then the “window-frame” debonded region growth rate method can be used to calculate an Arrhenius activation energy for the debonding process directly. If the coating exhibits significant resistance to cathodic debonding, then a different method must be used, because there may not be a measureable debonded area due to cathodic delamination for some time, or there may be no debonding until the coating fails catastrophically. For cathodic delamination resistant coatings, we are proposing that an Arrhenius activation energy or RAF can be calculated by measuring the effect of temperature difference between the operating and ALT temperatures on the rate of the cathodic

delamination reaction itself (equation 1). In the present case, the system is the zinc/monel 400 couple. A different metal couple would presumably exhibit a different RAF and Arrhenius activation energy. The table at the end of the experimental results section indicated the RAF for the zinc/monel 400 couple was 3.0; Equations 2 and 3 can be used to calculate the Arrhenius activation energy for the CD reaction in the zinc/monel 400 couple is approximately 3.8 kcal/mole.

The low values for the RAF and Arrhenius activation energy for the cathodic delamination reaction for the zinc/monel 400 alloy couple implies that the reaction itself is in a diffusion-limited regime for the temperature range of interest. Normally, chemical reactions have Arrhenius activation energies of approximately 20 kcal/mole or higher, but under the specified conditions, the cathodic delamination reaction exhibits an activation energy more like that for a diffusion process. The Arrhenius activation energy calculated for the increase in the width of the debonded area over time is significantly higher than the activation energy for the cathodic reaction itself (8.4 kcal/mole versus 3.8 kcal/mole). Thus, the cathodic delamination *debonding* reaction is more sensitive to temperature than the cathodic reaction (generation of hydroxyl ions) itself. This further implies that the actual debonding reaction/process is not particularly sensitive to the rate of hydroxyl generation on the cathodically polarized metal surface – but it is much more sensitive to temperature. Thus, it is more difficult to accelerate the aging of “good” coatings than “bad” coatings (because they resist the “debonding” reaction better than “bad” coatings). While its “RAF” may not be as high as one might have hoped, using the rate of the cathodic reaction (i.e., the generation of the polymer-metal bond destroying hydroxyl ions) does give the ALT designer a method for estimating the equivalent age of hardware with coatings resistant to cathodic delamination. More exotic methods, such as running the ALT in a pure oxygen atmosphere at several times normal atmospheric pressure may be necessary to increase the RAF of the cathodic reaction (equation 1) significantly.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Designing an ALT for “thin, infinite” coatings like paints under cathodic delamination promoting conditions is relatively straightforward. An Arrhenius activation energy can be calculated after one has measured the diffusivity of water through the paint at three different temperatures. When one considers “thick, finite” coatings with exposed polymer/metal bond lines, the ability to design an ALT splits along two lines of coating behavior. If the coating exhibits little or no resistance to cathodic delamination conditions, one can follow case (a) wherein the rate of the observed debonding at three different temperatures can be used to calculate the activation energy for the debonding process. The more difficult case is case (b) which covers coatings that have significant natural resistance to debonding under cathodic delamination-promoting conditions. In many cases with such coatings, the

debonding rate may be very difficult to quantify (because it is so slow), or it may even be non-existent until a resistant coating fails catastrophically. In such cases a RAF and activation energy can be calculated by directly measuring the rate of the cathodic reaction for the metal couple of interest. This has been done for the zinc/monel 400 couple, and the resulting RAF and reaction rate were found to be lower than the corresponding values for the debonding of the PRC-DeSoto primer/polyurethane system under cathodic delamination conditions. The reason(s) why this was so are not clear, but the implications of the results are that (1) the cathodic reaction is diffusion-limited for the temperature regime of interest for the zinc/monel 400 couple; and (2) the actual debonding *process* (the process by which the hydroxyl ions cause the PR-420 primer to debond from the monel 400 alloy) occurs much faster than the generation of the hydroxyl ions themselves. Thus, for the case of the zinc/monel 400 couple, the debonding rate of the PR-420 primer from the monel alloy under cathodic delamination supporting conditions is faster than the rate at which the cathodic debonding reaction generates hydroxyl ions. The implications of these results for the development of cathodic delamination resistant coatings is that approaches that focus on slowing or minimizing the debonding process for a particular polymer/metal combination will be more successful than approaches that focus on minimizing or even preventing the generation of hydroxyl ions via the cathodic reaction.

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